

MOLECULAR CHARACTERIZATION OF PREDATORS AND PARASITIDS ASSOCIATED WITH ONION INSECTS PESTS: CURRENT ADVANCES AND FUTURE PROSPECTS

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Abstract:

Onion (Allium cepa L.) is one of the most economically important vegetable crops which is cultivated all over the world [6]. Although its production is highly affected by insect's pests such as onion thrips, cutworms, onion maggots, aphids, and leaf miners [7,16,17,20]. Over use of chemical pesticides results in pesticides resistance in insect's pests, turns out to be harmful to beneficial insects, and harmful for environment, as well as human health [6]. So biological control by predators and parasitoids is been see as sustainable strategy for onion pest management [13,18]. For this biological control strategy accurate identification of natural enemies is essential for successful integrated pest management (IPM) technique [6,13]. Traditional morphological identification methods are usually difficult because many beneficial insects are extremely small, polymorphic, or exists as mysterious species [3,12]. Molecular characterization technique such as (PCR) polymerase chain reaction, DNA barcoding, mitochondrial DNA analysis, (RAPD) random amplified polymorphic DNA, (NGS) next-generation sequencing, and (RFLP) restriction fragment length polymorphism these techniques has improved the identification and polygenetic analysis of the beneficial insects. This technique provides species-specific identification and helps researchers to monitor biodiversity and improve biological control efficiency [4,5,10,11,15]. This review discusses about important onion insect's pests, associated predators and parasitoid, molecular characterization techniques, application in biological control, and future prospects for sustainable onion pest management [4,5,10].

Introduction

Onion is an important vegetable crop which is cultivated all over the world culinary purpose, medicinal, nutraceutical and commercial purpose [6]. India is the leading onion production countries, which is contributing in large amount to domestic consumption and export market [6]. Although, onion production is highly affected by several insect pests [7,16,17]. *Thrips tabaci* (Onion thrips) they are considered as one of the most harmful pests because they scrap leaf tissue and feed on sucking plant cell sap [7,16,18]. Other important pests included aphids, cutworms, leaf miner and onion maggots [17,20]. Various pests' invasion leads to reduced bulb quality, decreased in yield, and economic losses [7,1].

Many farmers mostly depend on chemical insecticides for pest management. Over use of pesticides has caused several problems such as environmental pollution, resistance of insecticide in insects, pest recovery, and harmful effect on human health as well as beneficial organisms [6]. Biological control using predators and parasitoids has become an environmentally friendly alternative for pest management [13,18]. Predators such as ladybird beetle, predatory mites, lacewings, and minute pirate bugs that feeds directly on insets pests, while parasitoids develop within hosts insects and in the end kill them [13,18,19].

Accurate identification predators and parasitoids is important for effective biological control [13,18]. Traditional taxonomy based on morphology sometimes becomes difficult because many useful insects have similar external characteristics or they exist as cryptic species complexes [3,12]. Advances in molecular biology has transformed insects' taxonomy by enabling DNA based identification methods [4,5]. Molecular characterization serves a powerful-tools for precise species identification, evolution of genetic variation, determine phylogenetics relationships, and also control biological control agents in agricultural ecosystem [4,5,10,11].

Major Insects Pests of Onion

There are many insects' pests that are responsible for impactful damage to onion crops [7,16,17]. Onion thrips are the most serious pest affecting onion cultivation all over the world [7,18]. Nymphs and adults both the stages of thrips feeds on leaves, producing grey streaks and reduce

photosynthetic efficacy [16,18]. Thrips attack can also spread viral transmission of *Iris Yellow Spot Virus* (IYSV) and few others [7,18].

Delia antiqua (onion maggot) is another serious pest after *Thrips tabaci*. The larva of onion maggots feed on onion roots and bulbs, which resulting in wilting, plant death and rotting [7]. Leaf miners create tunnels inside the leaf tissue, reducing plant health and photosynthesis [17]. Insects like aphid's damages onion plants sucking their plant sap and transmitting viral diseases [1,2]. Cutworm larva cuts young seedlings that are growing near soil surface and this causes heavy losses during early stages of crop growth [20].

For managing these pests effectively environmentally sustainable approaches are required [6,13]. Predators and parasitoids naturally lower the pest's population and also reduce the need of chemical pesticides [13,18]. Understangin the diversity and the biology of these natural enemies is far more important for integrated pest management system or programs [6, 13].

Predators and Parasitoids Associated with Onion Ecosystems.

Predators are free-living organisms that feeds on multiple prey individuals during their lifetime [13]. Ladybird beetles (*Coccinellidae*) are important predators of aphids and other insects that are soft bodies [1,3]. *Chrysoperla spp.* (Green Lacewings) are high impact predators that feeds on aphids, mites, and thrips [13]. *Orius spp.* (Minute pirate bugs) are widely known as most impactful predators of onion thrips [7,18]. Predatory mites also highly contribute in suppression of thrips populations under greenhouse protection [18].

Parasitoids are insects which develops inside or on the hosts body, sucking on hosts life force which eventually kills the host [13,19]. There are three types of parasitoids egg parasitoids, larval parasitoids, and pupa parasitoids. Parasitoids like egg parasitoids such as *Trichogramma* species that attacks on insect's eggs and prevents pest emergence [8,11]. Larval parasitoids attacks and develop inside or on the larval body such as caterpillars and leaf miners [14]. Pupal parasitoids develop inside hosts pupa and supress their development before emerging from pupa [13].

The success of biological control program depends on accurate identification of these beneficial organisms [13]. DNA based characterization provides a reliable means of differentiating closely

related species and to clarify ecological interactions between pests and their natural enemies [4,5,10,11].

Molecular Characterization Techniques

PCR – Polymerase chain reaction is world widely used molecular techniques for insect identification [5]. PCR allows selective amplification of specific DNA fragment using species-specific primer this technique is highly sensitive and requires minimal DNA sample [5]. A technique known as DNA barcoding, it uses short standardize DNA sequence for species identification [4]. The mtDNA or mitochondrial cytochrome oxidase I (COX-I) gene or also known as (COI) gene is world widely used as a universal barcode maker in insects [4]. DNA barcoding is useful for identifying closely related species, immature stages and also detecting cryptic species [2,4].

Mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA) markers such as COI, COII, and 16s rRNA are most frequently used insect's molecular studies because of their high mutation rate and maternal inheritance [15]. RFLP- Restriction fragment length polymorphism analysis identifies among organisms based on variations in restriction enzyme digestion patterns [5]. RAPD – Random amplified polymorphic DNA markers are useful for studying genetic diversity among insect's populations without prior sequence information [9].

NGS – Next-generation sequencing technology emerged as powerful tool for producing large-scale genomic data useful for phylogenetics, biodiversity research, population genomics, and gene exploration [5]. Advance technique including environmental DNA (eDNA), CRISPR-based diagnostics, and metagenomics have potential for further strengthen biological control research [5].

Applications, Challenges and Further Prospects

Molecular characterization has many important applications in biological control [5,10]. It helps researchers differentiate morphologically similar species, analyse host-parasitoids relationship, detect cryptic species complexes, and monitor released biological control agents [4,5,10,11]. Despite remarkable development, still many challenges remain. This molecular analysis requires expensive equipment, high-quality DNA, and skilled personal [5]. Due to limitation in genomic databases for some insect species restrict accurate identification [4,5]. Many developing countries may face difficulties in adopting advanced molecular techniques due to limitation of infrastructure and economic limitations [5].

Further research should focus on designing affordable low-cost molecular tools, enhancing insects DNA database and application of molecular method with integrated pest management programs [5,6]. Portable sequencing platform genomic methodologies are projected to make molecular characterization more affordable and efficient. In India integrating molecular tools in agricultural research and educational institutions can strengthen sustainable onion pest management while reducing the use of chemical pesticides [5].

In conclusion, biotechnology plays a very important role in improving the sustainable management of onion insect pest through the application of molecular characterization techniques [13,18]. Modern molecular techniques including PCR, DNA barcoding, and next-generating sequencing provide reliable identification of beneficial insects and improve our understanding in of valuable insights into pest-natural enemy interaction [4, 5]. The biotechnological approach contributes to biodiversity conservation and reform integrated pest management strategies [6]. Ongoing development in molecular biology and genomics

is expected to further strengthen biological control strategies and support eco-friendly onion production system [5, 13].

References

1. **Blackman, R. L., & Eastop, V. F. (2000).** Aphids on the World's Crops: An Identification and Information Guide. Wiley.
2. **Childers, C. C., & Achor, D. S. (1995).** Feeding and oviposition injuries to plants caused by thrips. *HortScience*, 30(5), 937–939.
3. **Furlong, M. J., Wright, D. J., & Dossall, L. M. (2013).** Diamondback moth ecology and management. *Annual Review of Entomology*, 58, 517–541.
4. **Footitt, R. G., Maw, H. E. L., Von Dohlen, C. D., & Hebert, P. D. N. (2008).** Species identification of aphids through DNA barcodes. *Molecular Ecology Resources*, 8(6), 1189–1201.
5. **Gullan, P. J., & Cranston, P. S. (2014).** The Insects: An Outline of Entomology. Wiley-Blackwell.
6. **Hebert, P. D. N., Cywinska, A., Ball, S. L., & deWaard, J. R. (2003).** Biological identifications through DNA barcodes. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B*, 270(1512), 313–321.
7. **Hoy, M. A. (2013).** Insect Molecular Genetics: An Introduction to Principles and Applications. Academic Press.
8. **Koul, O., Dhaliwal, G. S., & Cuperus, G. W. (2004).** Integrated Pest Management: Potential, Constraints and Challenges. CABI Publishing.
9. **Lewis, T. (1997).** Thrips as Crop Pests. CAB International.
10. **Luck, R. F., & Wajnberg, E. (2000).** Biological control and parasitoid diversity. *Annual Review of Entomology*, 45, 1–24.
11. **Nault, B. A., & Shelton, A. M. (2010).** Onion thrips and their management. *Annual Review of Entomology*, 55, 1–18.
12. **Pinto, J. D. (2006).** A review of the genus *Trichogramma*. *Annual Review of Entomology*, 51, 1–25.
13. **Roderick, G. K. (1996).** Geographic structure of insect populations. *Annual Review of Entomology*, 41, 325–352.
14. **Rueda, A., & Shelton, A. M. (1995).** Onion thrips damage and population dynamics in onion ecosystems. *Journal of Economic Entomology*, 88(5), 1405–1412.
15. **Smith, M. A., Rodriguez, J. J., Whitfield, J. B., et al. (2008).** Extreme diversity of tropical parasitoid wasps exposed by iterative integration of natural history, DNA barcoding, morphology, and collections. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 105(34), 12359–12364.
16. **Stouthamer, R., Hu, J., van Kan, F. J. P. M., Platner, G. R., & Pinto, J. D. (1999).** The utility of internally transcribed spacer 2 DNA sequences in differentiating sibling species of *Trichogramma*. *BioControl*, 43(4), 421–440.
17. **Triplehorn, C. A., & Johnson, N. F. (2005).** Borror and DeLong's Introduction to the Study of Insects. Thomson Brooks/Cole.
18. **Van Driesche, R., & Bellows, T. S. (1996).** Biological Control. Chapman and Hall.
19. **Whitfield, J. B. (1998).** Phylogeny and evolution of parasitoid wasps. *Annual Review of Entomology*, 43, 129–151.
20. **Zhang, D. X., & Hewitt, G. M. (1997).** Nuclear integrations: Challenges for mitochondrial DNA markers. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 12(7), 247–251.